

Table 1: Relations between the adaptation proposals and the different established ranges

Ranges (%)	Adaptation Proposal
0	Nothing / None
1-9	Very little / Very few
10-24	A little / Few
25	1 of 4 / 1 out of 4 / 1 in 4
26-40	1 of 3 / 1 out of 3 / 1 in 3
41-49	Almost half
50	Half
51-74	More than half
75	Most
76-90	A lot
91-99	Almost all / Almost very / Nearly the total
100	All / Very / The total
101-154	More than the total
155-254	Double
255-354	Triple
355+	N times the total

Table 2: Relations between the adaptation proposals and the different established ranges for cases related to units of measurement (e.g. Kg, L, etc.)

Ranges (%)	Adaptation Proposal
0	Nothing
1-24	Almost nothing
25-49	Less than half of 1
50	Half of 1
51-74	More than half of 1
75-90	Almost 1
100	1